

Role of Digitization in Admission Trends

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Abstract

Technology use is discussed and debated in practically every aspect of Education today. It is not hard to forget that the use of computers in Education is a very recent phenomenon that has only just become main stream. According to Roblyer and Edwards, the advent of the first microcomputers in 1997 marked the beginning of teachers having more control over the use of technology in the classroom. Many of the problems associated with technology use continue to be astonishingly constant even though technology use and application advance at a nearly exponential rate. These include suitably qualified employees, sufficient resources, continued funding, and successful technological integration to maximize learning. When these difficulties are successfully overcome, the benefits of utilizing technology can be increased while the drawbacks are reduced.

The International Society for Technology in Education summarizes the current problems that must be overcome in order to maximize a technology-integrated learning environment. As follows:

1. Visions supported by the education system's proactive leadership
2. Teachers adept in utilizing technology to enhance learning
3. Resources for the curriculum and content standards
4. student-centered methods of instruction
5. Evaluation of the Value of Technology in Education
6. providing technical support for using and maintaining technology resources
7. Community partners who offer knowledge, assistance, and face-to-face interactions
8. permanent financial assistance for continued technological use
9. New learning environments are supported by policies and standards.

Visions with the Support of the Education System and Active Leadership

The government's explanation and action plan for incorporating ICT into teaching, learning, and assessment practices in schools over the course of the following five years are laid out in the Digital Strategy for Schools. This approach to ICT integration builds on preceding ones and is aware of ongoing changes in the elementary and secondary education systems that are being made to the curriculum. The recommended activities are intended to completely integrate ICT across the system and improve the overall quality of Irish Education. This strategy focuses on the education sector, namely the school sector. The strategy has been carefully designed to make sure that the efforts and plans to support digital learning in the Higher Education and further education sectors are complemented and fit with the activities. This strategy was developed by the department based on

research. To establish a baseline for the levels of usage of ICT by teachers and schools, a census study was first carried out. A consultative report resulting from this research, Building Towards a Learning Society: A National Digital Strategy for Schools, was released in 2013, concurrently with the start of a public consultation phase. Various organizations and people submitted a total of 124 comments on the consultative paper's content, and these comments were supplemented by face-to-face meetings with a variety of stakeholder groups. In order to create the strategy, the input and opinions from this phase were then integrated with studies on the integration of ICT from around the world. The strategy incorporates the viewpoint of the younger generation.

The magnitude of the issue might be shown by the following statistics:

1. Readability ratings: According to the 2001 census, the nation's total literacy rate was 64.8%. This suggests that we lack the formal tools necessary to even attempt to identify the abilities of the other 35.2% of the population, let alone try to develop them. The nation's human resources are being underutilized to a very high degree.
2. Development of educational institutions: Between 2000–2001 and 2003–2004, there were 7.12 million primary schools, an increase of 6.38 million, or a simple annual growth rate of 3.87 percent. The number of Upper Primary Schools increased from 2.06 lakh to 2.62 lakhs within the same time period, representing a simple annual growth rate of 9.06 percent. The number of Plus, 2-level institutions, increased from 1.26 lac to 1.46 lac over the same time period, or a simple rate of growth of 5.29 percent per annum. The number of general education colleges increased from 7900 to 9400 within the same time period, representing a simple annual growth rate of 6.33 percent. We cannot expect to swiftly improve the

population's baseline educational status with the modest rate of expansion in the number of educational institutions. Consequently, the technical approach must also be backed and assisted by the conventional one. GOVERNMENT OF INDIAN MINISTRY OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION SECRET No. F.5-29/2007-DL Page of SECRET 6 interventions using ICT to make the information resources accessible to every learner at their convenience and at the right moment.

3. Student enrollment: The annual increases in enrollment for Primary, Upper Primary, and High/Higher Secondary classes between 2000-01 and 2003-04 were 4.24 percent, 4.59 percent, and 8.93 percent, respectively. It appears to be very difficult to close the gaps and utilize the full potential of our human resources at the current rate, barring the opening of alternate avenues.
4. Gross enrolment ratio: Since 1990–1991, the gross enrolment ratio for primary schools has been between 90–100%, yet even then, the literacy rate was just 64.8%, indicating that many pupils left school very early without acquiring literacy. The question of how they managed to enroll if they had to leave after a year or two or whether our pedagogy is so unappealing as to lose the interest of the young brains arises.
5. Dropout rates: For the academic years 2000–2001, 2002–2003, and 2003–2004, respectively, the dropout rates were 40.7 percent, 39.0 percent, 34.9 percent, and 31.5 percent.

Awareness of Educators in the Use of Technology for Learning

Teachers and principals will play a significant role in the ICT integration process. It is crucial to guarantee that ALL teachers have the skills, confidence, and knowledge required to use ICT in their teaching. Every stage of the teacher education continuum, including Initial Teacher Education, Induction, and Continuous Professional Development, must include the use of ICT for teaching, learning, and assessment. There will be several possibilities for teachers to advance their knowledge and self-assurance in implementing ICT integration, irrespective of where they are on the spectrum of teacher education. The relevance of the potential of ICT to improve teaching and learning in schools will be emphasized in the Teaching Council's policy on teacher education. The development of all upcoming possibilities for teacher professional learning will be significantly influenced by the UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers. ICT will be urged to be incorporated into the development and delivery of

CPD by The Online Planning for school systems – improving teaching, Education, and assessment, as well as other parties participating in teacher education, are all part of the department's support services. The approach will offer advice and examples of best practices for using ICT for teaching, learning, and assessment in a way that is efficient, critical, and ethical to schools. These illustrations will show actual classroom activities in action. Distributed leadership is required to fully integrate ICT into our educational system. ICT integration into teaching, learning, and evaluation in schools will be strongly supported by the department and its agencies. This won't be sufficient, though. So that we can integrate ICT and provide students with the digital skills we value, school management and other important stakeholders will also need to take the initiative and lead this task. The strategy acknowledges the critical position of assessment in keeping track of implementation and making sure the system is moving toward ICT integration. Institutions, along with other education providers, must record and share innovative practice with the greater teaching community in order to enhance the entire academic achievement of our children. By building a strong research foundation, every aspect of the system will be better educated on how to incorporate ICT. The strategy understands that there is a chance that ICT will be used unethically in schools, and the department will continue to offer advice, planning tools, and related services to help school administrators and teachers utilize ICT in a responsible, effective, and ethical manner. Additionally, the strategy will assist schools in establishing connections with already-existing school regulations, such as School Self Evaluation, to ensure that ICT is thoroughly ingrained throughout the school.

Content Standards and Curriculum Resources

The department has made investments in the ICT infrastructure of the nation in recent years, notably with the implementation of 100 Mbit/sec internet access to all post-primary institutions and a handful of special institutions with post-primary pupils. The Department of Learning and Employment and the Department of Communicating, Energy, and Natural Resources (DCENR) support this initiative. During the course of this strategy, primary schools will receive increased connectivity to improve internet access for all schools. The strategy has highlighted current developments, such as students bringing their own gadgets to class and the usage of cloud computing in Education. All of our lives are being impacted by the internet more and more. In light of these new developments, the strategy will offer guidance and assistance to schools, enabling both educators and administrators to make better local decisions. It also

acknowledges how difficult it is for institutions to obtain the required technical assistance. In order to provide guidance on the most appropriate choice for schools, the department will assess a variety of technical assistance possibilities. In order to verify that specifications and suggestions are offered for the purchase of equipment like printers, desktop PCs, and notebooks (SPU), the department will keep on collaborating with the Office of Government Procurement (OGP) and the School Procurement Unit. Schools will also need to upgrade their ICT infrastructure. The price of such equipment will be covered by financing in the sort of school grants.

It is critical to keep in mind that, in the modern era of technology use, going beyond merely increasing technology availability may be the toughest hurdle. Ely was thinking about the future when he proposed using technology to "restructure schools or to train higher order thinking" (Valdez et al., 1999, p. 14). To do this, instructors will undoubtedly require a range of experiences and Education to improve their professional abilities. As stated by Valdez et al. (1999), data-driven virtual learning is currently the main emphasis of the third phase. It's important to keep in mind that despite the fact that utilizing the internet has become a daily need, convenient access, and usage are still relatively new phenomena. There are other websites that offer timelines, but <http://www.zakon.org/robert/internet/timeline> is one that is particularly relevant. Finding suitable equipment and ongoing funding is a perennial challenge, given how swiftly technology is changing. Due to the expense, the public is demanding greater accountability and evidence of the advantages for pupils (Johnson & Bartleson, 2001; Valdez et al., 1999). As Internet usage rises, these contemporary educational challenges are mirrored, inspiring instructors to adapt technology to meet the needs of the standards movement and utilize it to proceed with greater-order thinking applications. Some districts have changed as a result of the based-on-data online educational setting on the internet. One such Technology Plan (Decatur School District 61, 1998) shows the advancements made by the subsequent phase of technology integration. It is clear that the technology's infrastructure and hardware were upgraded to the most modern models available at the time of Instructional Technology in Classroom 477. There was one computer lab in every elementary school, two in every middle school, and two to three in every high school. Mobile personal computers were furthermore accessible for use in the classroom. High-speed gain routes and proxy servers were used to link each personal computer to the internet. Within the Decatur Schools District, Cisco and Novell claim that this private institution has the most comprehensive and all-encompassing

networking infrastructure of any public school system in the country. The district's Fast Ethernet technology, according to the COMPAC Netelligent Case Study, "opens up a world of educational options and puts them at the top of the class" (Decatur Schools District 61, 1998, p.4). If districts want to provide students with a cutting-edge learning environment, they must continually assess and evaluate technological applications.

Student-Centered Approaches to Learning

To make the greatest use of the available technology, districts must create plans for the way they are going to reimburse for updates and continuous staff training. The mission statement for technology at Decatur School District 61 reads: "Developing lifetime learning opportunities utilizing innovative technology along with instruction, assistance programs, and connection to worldwide and local networks" (Decatur School District 61, 1998, p. 5). This important goal for all schools is mirrored in this mission statement. Although renting hardware is an option to consider, it's crucial to review the package being offered to make sure it includes data portability from the old technology to the new and operating system updates, software updates, and other essentials. Schools frequently struggle to provide cutting-edge equipment. Educators must employ a variety of tools, not simply cutting-edge technology, to enhance effective teaching and learning practices. By today's standards, this idea of the newest and best that is constantly evolving quickly is no longer relevant. Technology Taxonomy by Gerry Beimler (Decatur School District 61, 1998) serves as an excellent example of current significance and the challenges of moving up the teacher effectiveness hierarchy.

1. Computers are known to teachers with a certain level of understanding, and they may or may not use them. They are able to follow written directions that are keyed in step by step.
2. Application-level educators give the program control of the learning environment, but they are open to using or allowing students to use applications.
3. Teachers who are proficient in analysis can use apps' component parts to assist students in achieving their academic goals.
4. Teachers at the synthesis level may use relevant online learning methodologies and support resources with classroom instruction.
5. Evaluation-level teachers design and assess learning opportunities in the classroom in addition to developing instructional software and curricular materials (Decatur School District 61, 1998).

As with almost any effective implementation of curricular innovation, the teacher remains the main factor in the success of technological integration.

Ongoing Financial Support for Sustained Technology Use

Since the publication of Institutions IT 2000 (Department of Education, 1997), the Department of Education has been investing in the adoption of ICT in schools. This basic policy framework has been supplemented by later policy texts. The Department's Inspectorate assessed ICT usage in Irish schools in 2008. The succeeding paper, titled ICT in Schools, emphasizes the advantages of ICT use in schools while also highlighting amenities assistance with technical problems and ICT usage in teaching and learning concerns (Department of Education and Science, 2008). The ICT Strategy Group, which was created to provide guidance to the department on the ICT priorities for investment in Schools at the time, wrote the paper contributing efficiently to ICT in Institutions (Department of Education and Science, 2008). After Smart Schools=Smart Economy (Department of Education and Science, 2009) was published, the government granted schools with funds totaling €92 million. The most recent strategies and approaches for incorporating ICT into the classroom are presented in these publications. The goal of this strategy is to more successfully integrate ICT into schools by taking into account and building upon these policies. ICT'S IMPACTS ON TEACHING, TESTING, AND LEARNING The widespread usage of ICT in society today is changing the way individuals move through our daily lives. By linking policy regarding Education to social and economic progress, it has the power to impact alterations to ways teaching, learning, and assessment are carried out in schools.

For Maintaining and Using Technology Resources, Technical Assistance

Allowing all partners to effectively incorporate ICT into our classrooms and across the range of teacher preparation. The department will assess the execution of the strategy once a year. The

strategy expands on current Departmental policy, which aims to "provide all learners with the knowledge and abilities they require to participate entirely in society as well as the economy in general, in a manner that allows all pupils to acquire knowledge of how to learn" (Public Sector Reform Plan 2014-2016, 2014; p.43). This is done by making it possible for all students to pursue their academic goals. 17. The Strategy substantially enhances the continuing revolution of learning in primary and secondary schools (2015-2017) by supplementing the Department's Statement of Strategy. 18. THE INTEGRATION OF TECHNOLOGIES In order to achieve this goal, the department is committed to implementing an "ICT integration" strategy to integrate ICT across the system. ICT integration is a concept that is commonly used in national objectives and initiatives, but it is rarely defined. The expectation that ICT integration will happen spontaneously in schools only because ICT (such as computers, broadband, etc.) is there is all too common (Lim and Khine, 2006; OECD, 2015). However, it is becoming more widely understood that incorporating ICT into teaching, learning, and evaluation is a challenging and complex process (Qablan et al., 2009; Brown, 2004 in Jamieson-Proctor et al., 2006). Students who study digital media have access to the internet, communication tools, and computer technology for independent research. The capacity of pupils to understand exactly what they are searching for, reject or ignore some information, and recognize information that may be relevant or beneficial improves as they gain digital literacy abilities. They get the capacity to assess the various online information sources and challenge the points of view they come across. They learn how to communicate, collaborate, and create effectively.

Fig.1-Policies and standards supporting new learning environments

Policy Unit will support pertinent Departmental units, including the entities within its purview, in actively participating in the execution of the Digital Strategy for Schools. It is the duty of every department within the department, along with any pertinent affiliated organizations and support services, to integrate ICT at all stages of the continuum of teacher education. The department will also work with school administrators to incorporate ICT into their approaches to teaching, learning, and assessing pupils. It will be a difficult undertaking to accomplish meaningful integration; thus, every one of the instructional partners will need to collaborate.

Evaluation should be a significant component of the new strategy. It is essential to keep an eye on how the strategy is being put into practice to ensure that it is encouraging ICT inclusion in various schools. Ongoing ICT integration assessment is crucial for enhancing standards and results in this industry. The Department's Inspectorate's external evaluations, as well as internal evaluations conducted as a part of schools' commitment to self-evaluation, are both covered by this.

The application of technological devices in Education, instruction, and evaluation was recommended, and the strategy was suggested to encourage teacher-led research in this area. Several replies made during the strategy's public consultation phase supported the idea of teachers as reflective practitioners.

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